

Wastewater Management Challenges and Solutions in Tanzania: A Case Study of Dar es Salaam City

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Abstract

This study investigates the wastewater management challenges and solutions in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, amidst rapid urbanization and population growth. Dar es Salaam, the largest city in Tanzania, is experiencing severe difficulties due to inadequate infrastructure, insufficient financial resources, ineffective governance, and lack of proper planning. As the population has surged from 3.87 million in 2010 to an estimated 8.56 million by 2025, the volume of generated wastewater has overwhelmed existing treatment facilities, resulting in untreated sewage being discharged into local water bodies. This situation poses significant public health risks and contributes to environmental degradation. The research highlights the need for improved wastewater management practices and explores various innovative technologies, such as Anaerobic Digestion (AD), that can address these pressing challenges. It also underscores the importance of community engagement, robust regulatory frameworks, and sustainable funding mechanisms to enhance the effectiveness of wastewater management strategies. The study concludes that a holistic approach is essential to realizing significant improvements, thereby safeguarding public health and securing water resources for the rapidly growing population of Dar es Salaam.

Keywords: *Wastewater management, Dar es Salaam, Urbanization, Population growth, Anaerobic digestion, Community engagement.*

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Introduction

The rapid population growth in the last few decades has led fast urbanization and industrialization posing a challenge of increase of quantity and composition of wastes released to the environment (Nayeri et al., 2024). Anthropogenic pollution plays an important part in deteriorating the water quality of rivers all over the world, especially in urban areas of Africa where water quality monitoring is still seriously constrained by the limited test facility and capability. In densely populated urban areas of many developing countries, water scarcity, poor water quality, and inadequate wastewater management present complex challenges to ensuring health and wellbeing (Yao, Han, Wang, Friese, Wang, Zuo, Kimirei, Kishe, Gao, & Xiong, 2023).

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are facilities used to treat domestic and industrial wastewater. Various processes (e.g., physical, chemical, and biological) are combined to remove pollutants from industrial or human activities to minimize environmental and human health damage caused by wastewater from WWTPs (Hreiz et al., 2015). Sewage sludge is the waste residue from primary/secondary

sedimentation tanks and other linked equipment in the wastewater treatment process (Bolobajev et al., 2014), which has potential ecological hazards due to the residual organic matter and heavy metals from treated wastewater.

Without proper management, it can lead to serious environmental issues, such as odors, disease transmission, heavy metal bioaccumulation and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Singh et al., 2011). Sustainable management and utilization of sludge formed during wastewater treatment require a systematic analysis of the environmental impacts emanating from these processes to avoid negative impacts and adverse risks to the environment and the living things (Hao et al., 2019).

According to Eurostat statistics, sewage sludge production in the European Union amounts to about 15 million tons of dry solids (DS) in 2020. Statistics from “Report on the State of the Ecology and Environment in China 2022” showed that the total capacity of China’s urban WWTPs was 58.46 billion cubic meters in 2021. The annual production of urban sewage sludge in China was approximately 13.6 million tons (DS). Meanwhile, agriculture use and incineration are the main disposal methods in European countries, accounting for 32.96% and 32.56% of total disposal, respectively (Yu et al., 2023).

Dar es salaam is characterized by poor and decentralized waste water management systems where by only 10% of the population is connected to the sewer network. The majority of the population use on-site systems, with 20% of total households using on-site septic tanks and the remaining 70% using on-site pit latrines. Inadequate sanitation is an underlying cause behind the extended outbreak of waterborne diseases like cholera which resulted in over 10,000 reported cases and a mortality rate of 1.6 % between 2015 and 2017.

About 90% of Dar es Salaam residents need to pay for pit or septic tank emptying services carried out by using trucks. Current pit emptying services are either expensive vacuum tankers or unsafe self-emptying practices. Illegal dumping of wastewater is evident in most parts of the streets in the city due to the limited number of sludge treatment sites. It is estimated that nearly 60% of the on-site systems are using his local and unsafe ‘vomiting’ method of emptying. This process is carried out to allow un treated waste water from pit latrines to flow and spread into surface and ground water.

Figure 1. Dar es Salaam, Administrative Structure
Source: (Todd et al., 2019)

Large quantity of fecal pollution is directed to the water bodies especially Indian ocean directly or through the streams flowing through the city that pour their contents there. Although there is limited data on microbial and pathogen loads associated with this pollution. Surrounding Dar es Salaam, there are a number of coral reef ecosystems that are important marine habitats for both fishing and eco-tourism. (Conservancy, 2021).

Several studies have been conducted on wastewater management challenges and solutions in Tanzania particularly fast-growing cities like Dar es salaam. According to (Wawa, 2020) water and sanitation authorities in the cities are facing a challenge of fast-growing populations with shortage of funds for extension and rehabilitation of infrastructure. A minimal use of the available wastewater systems by the current population due to high cost associated with installation and management processes.

Poor technology used and aging infrastructures development led to formation of policies that cannot support a rapid growing population. Resilient wastewater treatment systems require acceleration of assets replacement, preparedness, installation of alternative power supply, community engagement, policies and plans enforcement (Sweya et al., 2018). Domestic and industrial sewage and wastewater are discharged untreated into streams and rivers. Institutional analysis and research findings revealed that Government and institutional ineffectiveness, through poor town planning and corruption, have produced the conditions through which these discharges have the greatest impact (Wilson, 2015) . This study aims to Identify key practices, successes, failures and explore future prospects in wastewater management practices in Dar es salaam, Tanzania.

Materials and Methods

A systematic search and review of the peer-reviewed and grey literature from electronic databases like ScienceDirect, JSTOR, SCOPUS, PubMed and Web of Science were well consulted to identify articles related the problem. Table 1 below, illustrates the summary of the articles, themes and findings collected and analyzed.

Table 1. Wastewater Challenges, Technologies and Prospects in Dar es Salaam

Themes Studied	Findings	Citations
Current wastewater treatment status in in Dar es salaam	Inadequate infrastructure, Frequent blockages Insufficient treatment facilities Limited treatment capacity Seasonal flooding Aging infrastructure, Environmental pollution Inadequate treatment facilities, Overflow during rainy seasons Reliance on informal solutions like pit latrines	(Nayeri et al., 2024), (Yao, Han, Wang, Friese, Wang, Zuo, Kimirei, Kishe, Gao, Xiong, et al., 2023), (Wawa, 2020), (Hreiz et al., 2015), (Bolobajev et al., 2014), (Singh et al., 2011), (Fernández-Arévalo et al., 2017), (Yu et al., 2023), (Todd et al., 2019), (Conservancy, 2021), (Wawa, 2020), (Sweya et al., 2018), (Wilson, 2015), (review, 2025), (Worrall et al., 2017), (Catherine & Augustina, 2022), (EWURA, 2020), (HABITAT, 2021).
Technologies applied in wastewater treatment	Decentralized Wastewater Treatment Systems Septic tanks and pit latrines, Faecal Sludge Management Conventional Activated Sludge Constructed Wetlands Industrial Wastewater Treatment Systems	(Catherine & Augustina, 2022; Wawa, 2020), (NEMC, 2007), (Kasala et al., 2016), (Datola, 2023), (Ruhinda et al., 2024), (Chaggu et al., 2002b), (Sinharoy et al., 2019), (Africa, 2014)

Impacts of poor wastewater treatment practices	Diseases outbreaks, Air pollution due to odors, Climate change, Loss of biodiversity Eutrophication	(Yao, Han, Wang, Friese, Wang, Zuo, Kimirei, Kishe, Gao, & Xiong, 2023), (Lema, 2025), (Gutterer et al., 2009), (Kitole et al., 2024), ((WHO), 2018), (Singh et al., 2024), (Monachese et al., 2025), (Corcoran, 2010)
Wastewater policy and regulatory framework and Wastewater management challenges	No specific regulations, Weak compliance monitoring, Limited private sector participation	(MINISTRY OF WATER, 2023), (Bahri, 2015), (Guest et al., 2009), (De Troyer et al., 2016), (Kitole et al., 2024).
Prospects in wastewater management in	Population is growing very fast in developing cities Circular economy and renewable energy are a sustainable solution to alleviate the challenge.	(Siddiqui et al., 2023), (Kalderén, 2019), (CAMBI, 2022), (Huang, 2024), (Msaki et al., 2022), (Obileke et al., 2023), (Akinbomi et al., 2022).

Source: Authors

Dar es salaam is the largest city in Tanzania and the fastest growing in Africa. It is located in the north-eastern coast along the Indian ocean. As of 2024, Dar es Salaam's population is estimated to be **8,161,230 which is approximately 8,100 people per square mile** (3,100 per square kilometer). The city is the most industrialized region and the largest commercial center in the country. Key economic activities include trade and commerce, industrial manufacturing, services and tourism (review, 2025). It is the powerhouse of Tanzania with the port of Dar es Salaam as a vital hub for international trade, facilitating the import and export of goods. The city hosts numerous industries, including textiles, food processing, and construction materials which make it a center for services like banking, transport, communication and other services, attracting businesses and professionals from across the region.

Figure 2. The Population of Tanzania's Six Largest Cities, 1950–2030

Source: Worrall et al., 2017

Around 75% of the city's residents live in informal settlement areas, characterized by inadequate infrastructure and services. This rapid growth often outpaces the development of essential utilities, including wastewater treatment systems. Unplanned settlements with poor or lack proper sanitation infrastructure, leading to open defecation and improper disposal of waste. Pit latrines or septic tanks, results to contamination of groundwater and local water bodies and pose a public health risks (Catherine & Augustina, 2022).

Results

The EWURA has reported that the approximate annual wastewater production in Dar es Salaam is around 300 million M³ (EWURA, 2020). Only 25% of Dar es Salaam's wastewater is collected and treated. The rest flows untreated through the streets, into rivers, and eventually into the Indian Ocean, endangering marine life. In Kariakoo, clogged sewers spill dirty water into the streets, mixing with rainwater to create potentially harmful sludge. The stench is unbearable, posing severe health risks to city dwellers (Earth, 2024). Approximately 4,013 tons per day, which translates to around 1,460,945 tons per year have been revealed by UN-Habitat. Despite the high volume of wastewater produced, a significant challenge lies in the management of this wastewater, especially in unplanned urban settlements characterized by poor sanitation leading to a considerable amount of wastewater is either not treated or is managed poorly (HABITAT, 2021). Over 90% of residents depend on on-site sanitation systems which tends to overflow during the rainy season resulting to mixing of raw sewage and stormwater. The cost of maintaining and emptying pit latrines and septic tanks are not affordable for many residents and hence untreated wastewater from on-site sanitation systems to contaminate local water bodies, leading to waterborne diseases like cholera, typhoid and environmental degradation (Yap et al., 2023), (Akpor & Muchie, 2011), (Lam et al., 2015).

Poor Wastewater Management Systems

Untreated wastewater water contains organic matter, pathogens, and chemicals which leads to a serious pollution in water bodies which poses a threat to the ecosystems. Affected soil is potentially harmful for plant growth and results to less agricultural produce (Literacy, 2024). Toxic substances like heavy metals, pharmaceuticals, and microplastics from industrial and domestic products are found in wastewater. When released to the water bodies they cause death and loss of biodiversity because of destruction of their habitats and interference with their lifecycles. Treatment of wastewater may lead to emission of GHG to the environment which leads to global warming and climate change.

Excessive nutrients from untreated wastewater can cause eutrophication which cause dense growth of plant life in water bodies, leading to oxygen depletion and death of aquatic animals (Conservancy, 2025). The study by (Yao, Han, Wang, Friese, Wang, Zuo, Kimirei, Kishe, Gao, & Xiong, 2023) to investigate the water quality of urban rivers in Dar es Salaam namely Mzinga River, Kizinga River, and Msimbazi river revealed a severe pollution with nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), with pollution increasing from upstream to downstream with "poor" quality. Unregulated discharges of untreated municipal and industrial wastewaters were identified as the main drivers of water quality.

The steady increase in anthropogenic pressures on this natural resource caused by continuous human population growth and urbanization is alarming and requires an urgent balance between wastewater discharge and protection of the receiving water bodies (Burian et al., 2000). The higher the population the higher freshwater requirements and consequently higher wastewater production. Serious water crises such as water scarcity and pollution have been a barrier to the future socio-economic developments (Corcoran, 2010). The rapid population growth in Dar es salaam has significant impact on the production and management of wastewater. Over the past decade, the city's population has increased from approximately 3.87 million in 2010 to 8.56 million in 2025, with an average annual growth rate of around 5.77% (LLC, 2025). This rapid growth has placed immense pressure on the existing wastewater infrastructure, leading to several challenges.

With more people, the volume of wastewater generated increases while wastewater treatment plants remain almost the same for decades leading to a struggle to meet rising demands resulting in untreated or partially treated wastewater being discharged into the environment. Shortage of funds makes it difficult to build and maintain wastewater treatment plants and to put in place appropriate monitoring and enforcement systems. Limited financial investments lead to underdeveloped infrastructure and reduced

capacities for maintenance and operation, exacerbating sanitation challenges (Yap et al., 2023), (Lema, 2025). Effective planning and infrastructure development must keep pace with population growth to mitigate health risks and environmental degradation. Insufficient investment in maintenance, lack of trained personnel, and poor governance contribute to ineffective wastewater management. As a result untreated sewage affecting nearby water bodies, leading to health hazards for communities relying on these water sources (NEMC, 2007), (Wawa, 2020).

The growth of industries in Dar es Salaam leads to increased volumes of wastewater generated, often containing complex mixtures of pollutants. Industries release toxic substances that are challenging to treat, thus complicating treatment processes. The high biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) from industrial wastewater can overwhelm municipal treatment systems, leading to decreased treatment efficacy and increased operational challenges. The governance structures in place often fail to integrate sanitation and wastewater management into urban planning. Insufficient human resources, technical expertise, and coordination among relevant authorities contribute to ineffective planning and implementation of wastewater management strategies in most cities of the developing nations Tanzania inclusive (Lema, 2025). Institutional fragmentation and the absence of comprehensive land use policies hinder the systematic development of sanitation infrastructure necessary for the burgeoning population (Sinharoy et al., 2019).

In areas with unplanned developments, lack of effective regulation and monitoring of industrial discharges exacerbates wastewater management issues. This situation is particularly problematic where informal industries do not comply with environmental standards. The absence of integrated industrial and municipal wastewater management strategies hampers efforts to protect water resources. Industrial contaminants and emerging pollutants necessitates advanced treatment technologies, which often require significant financial investment and specialized operational expertise which is a burden on local governments and utility companies (Datola, 2023), (Sinharoy et al., 2019).

Health and Environmental Impacts of Poor Wastewater Management Practices

Inadequate treatment and discharge of wastewater can lead to the contamination of water sources causing ill health when this water is consumed or utilized by human beings. Common waterborne diseases include cholera, dysentery, and typhoid fever. A report from the World Bank in 2017, approximately 4,985 cases of cholera were reported in Tanzania, largely attributed to poor sanitation ((WHO), 2018). In densely populated areas, such as Dar es Salaam, the risk of disease outbreaks is heightened when waste is improperly managed. The 2016 Demographic and Health Survey indicated that 55% of Tanzania's population lacked access to improved sanitation, contributing to a public health crisis (Kitole et al., 2024) .

Poorly managed wastewater leads to the contamination of rivers, lakes, and coastal waters. In Dar es Salaam, untreated effluent is commonly discharged into the ocean and nearby water bodies, adversely affecting aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity. The introduction of nutrients from untreated wastewater into freshwater systems can lead to eutrophication depleting oxygen in the water.

This kills fish and disrupt aquatic life as have been reported in environmental assessments of the coastal waters in Tanzania (Yao, Han, Wang, Friese, Wang, Zuo, Kimirei, Kishe, Gao, Xiong, et al., 2023). Poor disposal of wastewater contaminates the land with heavy metals and pathogens which affect agricultural productivity of the land and risks food security through the food chain (Lema, 2025).

Emerging contaminants like pharmaceuticals, personal care products, microplastics, and other chemicals from the industries are increasingly found in wastewater. These chemicals if not properly monitored, can lead to various health issues, including hormonal disruptions, reproductive problems, and increased cancer risk. Also, they may accumulate in aquatic ecosystems, leading to long-term ecological damage (Singh et al., 2024), (Kalderén, 2019). The unmanaged discharge of wastewater into the environment compromises urban ecosystems' ability to cope with climate change impacts. The growth of urban areas

without adequate infrastructure can lead to increased flooding, exacerbated by the degradation of natural drainage systems due to pollution and waste build-up (Monachese et al., 2025).

Wastewater Policy and Regulatory Framework

The wastewater policy and regulatory framework in Tanzania is evolving to address the challenges posed by rapid urbanization and population growth. It is shaped by various legislative measures aimed at managing water quality and wastewater effectively while considering the interests of safe organisms and the environment. The draft national water policy 2002 version 2023 discuss in details the legal, regulatory and political aspects addressing the gaps and challenges to provide focus for the current framework and its implications (MINISTRY OF WATER, 2023). The Water Resources Management Act of 2009 and the Water Supply and Sanitation Act of 2019 establish essential guidelines and regulations for managing wastewater alongside freshwater resources. These acts are designed to facilitate sustainable water resource management and ensure safe sanitation practices. The Environmental Management Act No. 20 of 2004 addresses pollution control and emphasizes the need for environmental assessments in projects that could impact water quality. The Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority Act, 2001 outlines the regulatory body's role in overseeing water supply and sanitation, including the treatment and disposal of wastewater in urban areas, ensuring compliance with standards that protect public health and the environment. Specific regulations mandate municipalities and private operators to manage wastewater treatment facilities, implement proper sewage disposal solutions, and adhere to quality control measures for treated water. The Act emphasizes the importance of community-based approaches in managing water supply and sanitation services in operations and decision making.

Treatment Technologies Applied in Tanzania

Depending on variables including population density, available resources, and legal frameworks, many technologies are used to treat wastewater, and each is appropriate for a particular context and area. Several scholars (Kasala et al., 2016), (Ruhinda et al., 2024), (Wawa, 2020), (Chaggu et al., 2002a), (Msaki et al., 2022) have studied different technologies applied in waste water treatment in Tanzania including their advantages and limitations. Conventional Activated Sludge (CAS) Systems is one of the most frequently used technologies utilized in Dar es Salam. The CAS involve aerating wastewater to promote the growth of microorganisms that digest organic matter. After aeration, the mixed liquor is settled in a clarifier, separating treated water from the sludge. Sludge can further be treated and reused in various ways including agriculture and animal feeding. This technology is used in larger urban centres such as Dar es Salaam and Mwanza. Another pertinent method is the Constructed Wetlands which are engineered systems that mimic natural wetlands. They use vegetation and microbial communities to treat wastewater through filtration and biological processes. Constructed wetlands can be a low-cost alternative for wastewater treatment. It is applied in both urban and rural areas, including sites near Dodoma and some regions around Dar es Salaam (NEMC, 2007) .

Industries in Tanzania are increasingly adopting wastewater treatment systems to comply with environmental regulations. However, these systems vary depending on the type of industry and the specific pollutants involved. Industrial wastewater treatment systems in Tanzania are evolving, focusing on compliance with environmental regulations while addressing the unique challenges posed by different industrial sectors. Modern technology, investment and skilled workforce is required to deal with industrial wastewater (Africa, 2014). Decentralized Wastewater Treatment Systems (DEWATS) offer modular solutions that can treat wastewater near its source, reducing the need for extensive sewer systems. DEWATS utilize simple technologies like anaerobic treatment followed by constructed wetlands. It is the dominant practice in Dar es salaam although its primary challenge is inadequate treatment efficiency in reducing key pollutants such as Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), and total coliform levels (Gutterer et al., 2009), (Catherine & Augustina, 2022).

Prospects of Wastewater Treatment in Dar es Salaam

The issues surrounding wastewater management have grown more pressing since Dar es Salaam's population is predicted to nearly quadruple by the mid-2030s due to the city's ongoing rapid urbanisation. Around 70% of the city's population currently lives in informal settlements, where there are very poor sanitary facilities. Since just 10% of the population is served by the formal sewerage network, a more thorough and sustainable method of wastewater treatment is desperately needed. Taking in to account rapid expanding population and sanitation issues Anaerobic Digestion technologies can assist Dar es Salaam in the long run, get rid of challenges associated with mismanagement of wastewater (McFarlane et al., 2014).

Case Study – Mbezi Beach Anaerobic Digestion (AD) Wastewater Treatment Project

The Mbezi Beach Anaerobic Digestion (AD) Wastewater Treatment Project was a project introduced for the purpose of enhancing wastewater management and reducing environmental pollution in Dar es Salaam. Situated in the Kinondoni District of Dar es Salaam it has a 16,000 m³/day wastewater treatment capacity. It is owned by the Dar es Salaam Water Supply and Sanitation Authority (DAWASA) and designed by Metito, a provider of water management technologies (Metito, 2024). As of the latest updates, the Mbezi Beach facility is fully operational. This means that it has successfully transitioned from construction to actual wastewater treatment activities. The plant is actively receiving and processing wastewater, which signifies that it is functioning as intended.

The project employs conventional activated sludge technology with anaerobic digesters are used to produce biogas from the sludge and combined heat and power (CHP) generation system. This system reduces electric power consumption by approximately 40% at the plant's ultimate capacity. Within its sort period of full operation, the project has the following achievements and challenges as observed to help in preparing a better future in wastewater management and ensuring human health and environmental protection. This has allowed for the production of biogas, contributing to energy recovery and sustainability. It has significantly improved sanitation in the city, reducing the incidence of waterborne diseases and enhancing public health. The project has made a remarkable milestone towards greenhouse emission reduction by utilization of methane gas which is used as a source of fuel. The project has created skilled jobs among local workers and improved knowledge and supports the economic and industrial development.

The project is facing a number of challenges which require measures as suggested bellow in order to make operate successfully. The treatment facility encounters higher-than-anticipated wastewater inflows due to rapid urbanization therefore it may not operate at optimal capacity, leading to untreated sewage overflow. This calls for expansion of infrastructure or the addition of supplementary treatment processes.

There is a shortage of sustainable funding model to support ongoing maintenance, operational costs, and future upgrades. Maintenance of advanced technologies like AD systems is expensive. Inadequate regulatory frameworks or enforcement mechanisms could diminish the effectiveness of treatment processes and lead to environmental compliance issues. A strong regulatory frameworks and enforcement mechanisms is required to ensure compliance with environmental standards. Monitoring and evaluation framework to regularly assess the facility, identify challenges, and respond with adaptive strategies (2023, 2023).

Discussion

Waste water management challenges in the city of Dar es salaam are sandwiched in a complex interaction of economic, social and political constrains. These challenges including but not limited to inadequate infrastructure, financial constraints, ineffective governance, and significant public health implications

need an integrated and multidisciplinary approach to solve. The city's aging and insufficient wastewater treatment systems struggle to accommodate a rapidly growing population, leading to the discharge of untreated sewage into water bodies. Financial limitations impede the development and maintenance of necessary facilities, while weaknesses in governance and regulatory frameworks exacerbate sanitation issues. Innovative projects like the Mbezi Beach Anaerobic Digestion Treatment Project show potential for technological solutions but face operational and funding challenges (Omohwovo, 2024).

A significant deficit in wastewater treatment infrastructure, leading to frequent blockages and insufficient capacity to handle the volume of sewage generated. This inadequacy is exacerbated by the aging infrastructure that struggles to meet the demands of a rapidly growing population. Many residents rely on informal solutions like pit latrines, which are not only unsustainable but also pose severe health risks. To combat this issue, there is an urgent need for investments in resilient wastewater treatment systems that can adapt to changing urban dynamics and demographic pressures (Wawa, 2020). The financial limitations faced by water and sanitation authorities are evident in the findings. The lack of funds for infrastructure extension and rehabilitation leads to minimal use of wastewater systems, which further compounds the problem of untreated sewage discharge into rivers and streams. (Kasala et al., 2016) examined the role of NGOs and community participation in eliminating the problem though it encounters the technical challenge related to capacity and efficiency.

The impact of ineffective governance and regulatory frameworks on wastewater management. Government and institutional ineffectiveness, influenced by poor town planning and corruption, leads to systemic failures that exacerbate sanitation issues. Strengthening governance through improved regulatory frameworks and enforcement mechanisms is essential for ensuring compliance with environmental standards. A collaborative approach, engaging local communities, is vital to foster accountability and enhance transparency in wastewater management practices.

A critical link between wastewater management and public health is revealed with extremes in congested peri urban areas. The discharge of untreated sewage poses severe health risks, particularly in urban areas where communities are already vulnerable. Improved management practices could significantly reduce incidences of waterborne diseases, enhance overall public health, and contribute to the wellbeing of the population. Educational campaigns aimed at raising awareness among communities about the importance of sanitation and their roles in improving local wastewater management is urgently needed (Safari et al., 2019)

Anaerobic Digestion (AD) as Solution Dar es Salam's Waste Water Problem

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a biological process used in wastewater treatment to break down organic matter in the absence of oxygen. This process occurs in specialized, sealed vessels called anaerobic digesters or bioreactors. For a number of decades (AD) is considered one of the best options for sludge treatment, even in areas experiencing rapid population growth and industrial development (Siddiqui et al., 2023). This process is also utilized by a range of industries, food processing waste, slaughterhouse waste and sewage sludge treatment or management (CAMBI, 2022). Anaerobic digestion (AD) is highly recommended process in sludge treatment because of the possibility of energy recovery from methane and sludge volume reduction can be achieved.

Apart from it being a complete treatment method, all conventional disposal approaches need anaerobic digestion as pre-treatment. That is to say AD is an intermediate state of treatment processes of waste sludge. The end use of sludge is mainly for landfill or agriculture application. Treated sludge may be used as composition of brick or cement is the mainstream of conventional material valorization although recent attention has been drawn to sludge derived biochar, due to the potential improvement on soil quality and reduction of uptake of heavy metals by crops (Singh et al., 2014). AD has the ability to stabilize sewage sludge and significantly reduce pathogens, making it safer for disposal or use as a fertilizer in agriculture. This process can achieve a level of sanitization that meets environmental and health

regulations for the reuse of treated sludge, thus minimizing public health risks associated with pathogens and heavy metals in untreated sludge (Bertanza et al., 2016). Anaerobic digestion not only reduces the volume of sewage sludge but also generates biogas, a renewable energy source rich in methane. This biogas can be utilized for electricity and heat generation, contributing to energy independence for wastewater treatment plants (Raheem et al., 2018) .

Also, AD enables the recovery of nutrients, notably nitrogen and phosphorus, from sewage sludge. The digestate produced after AD can be further processed to extract these essential nutrients, promoting a circular economy in nutrient management. The recovered nutrients is used to produce fertilizers, addressing concerns regarding nutrient depletion in agricultural practices and creating sustainable agricultural systems (Alengebawy et al., 2024), (Yang et al., 2024). AD is effective in degrading a wide variety of organic pollutants, including pharmaceuticals and personal care products, often found in sewage sludge. The anaerobic conditions and microbial activity can help minimize the concentration of these emerging contaminants. AD can reduce the levels of certain pollutants, making the treated sludge more suitable for land application or further processing. This is an essential consideration in regions where industrial discharges may introduce new contaminants into the water system (Huang, 2024), (Obileke et al., 2023) .

Anaerobic digestion systems can be designed to handle varying scales of sludge treatment, from small community plants to large municipal facilities. This flexibility makes AD a suitable option for regions undergoing rapid urbanization and changes in wastewater characteristics due to industrial development. It can also be adapted to different types of organic waste, including industrial by products, thus allowing for a versatile approach to sludge management in diverse urban settings (Akinbomi et al., 2022), (Kegl et al., 2025). AD significantly reduces greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions compared to other sludge treatment methods like incineration or landfilling. By converting waste to energy and returning nutrients to soil, AD supports sustainability and reduces environmental impacts (Alengebawy et al., 2024), (Huang, 2024).

Conclusion

The study highlights the urgent need for improved wastewater management in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, where over 90% of the population lacks access to adequate sewage systems as rapid urbanization and population growth exacerbate existing challenges. The key issues identified include inadequate infrastructure, limited financial resources, ineffective governance, and insufficient planning, which contribute to the discharge of untreated sewage into local water bodies, posing severe health risks and environmental degradation.

The case of the Mbezi Beach Anaerobic Digestion Wastewater Treatment Project demonstrates potential pathways to enhance wastewater management through technological innovation and energy recovery while addressing public health concerns. Apart from providing a light towards sustainable wastewater management solutions, it also highlights the possibility of energy and resources recovery which reduces operation costs and reduce GHG emissions which contribute to climate change.

However, challenges such as the rising volumes of wastewater due to urban growth and the complexities of maintaining advanced treatment technologies must be tackled through sustainable funding mechanisms and robust regulatory frameworks. A collaborative approach involving government, local authorities, and communities will be crucial to ensure compliance with environmental standards, improve treatment efficacy, and safeguard water resources. Generally, addressing the multifaceted issues of wastewater management in Dar es Salaam requires a holistic strategy that encompasses financial investment, capacity building, and community engagement to foster sustainable development and protect public health.

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